

The Use of Soil Moisture Sensors and Arduino Interface to Create an Automatic Watering Device for Houseplants

¹Dave B. Buragay PhD, ²Lance Emmanuel M. Escalona, ³Louie Ashley B. Aniag, ⁴Putli Tarhata R. Laja, ⁵Krisnelle Mae T. Escobar, ⁶Flynt Keiran A. Diaz, ⁷Prince Rovi C. Salenga

¹Research Adviser, ^{2,3,4,5,6,7}Student
Senior High School Department
Philippine School Doha, Doha, Qatar.

Abstract- The COVID-19 pandemic is associated with an upturn toward home gardening as a relaxing activity, bringing a sense of peace and proximity to nature during the quarantine measures. Subsequently, after COVID-19, irregular watering patterns become a threat that houseplants face. They are poisoned by root rot from overwatering or dehydration from underwatering. To solve this problem, this study introduces an Automatic Watering Device that relies on soil moisture sensors and Arduino interfaces. The quantitative experimental research method was used to determine the accuracy of the automatic watering device, the volume of water dispensed, the relay module's response time, the water pumping time, and the soil moisture sensor detection time. The result of this study proved the feasibility of using soil moisture sensors and an Arduino interface in creating an Automatic Watering Device as it displays a laudable rate of accuracy in comparison to a standard moisture meter with an average of 97.76%, with a highly accurate detection time at 7.50 seconds on average. Soil moisture sensors and an Arduino interface were utilized to create an affordable, convenient and accurate Automatic Watering Device, contributing to a big step towards automation in plant care, due to its efficiency, sustainability and improved plant well-being. The proven effectiveness, based on the results, in detecting low moisture levels and the accurate watering confirmed wider options for usage in automated plant caring systems. Lastly, it is recommended to better utilize the device's automation and reduce the hands-on involvement of the plant owner by developing an app that can perform tasks such as set watering intervals, control the amount of water delivered, select for specific plant types through the app, and turn the whole device on and off.

Index Terms: Arduino Interface, Soil moisture sensor, Automatic Watering Device, Houseplants, Plant health, , Plant-Based Services

I. INTRODUCTION

The COVID-19 pandemic affected everything from education, economic, business, health, and even recreational activities. Due to quarantine restrictions, people were mandated to stay in their respective homes which led to the adaptation to the new normal. Home gardening is one activity that people were engaged in during the onset of lockdown up to this point wherein COVID-19 has lied low. Home gardening has become a widespread leisure activity for people since then. Indoor plants offer relief, focus, cheer, company, and a connection to nature during COVID-19, resulting in a significant increase in sales (Phillipz & Schulz, 2021). The COVID-19 pandemic is over and therefore the plant owners are back to their normal lives which require them to attend their duties away from home and hence the plants are watered in irregular intervals. But in case of indoor plants there can be an adverse effect if they are either overwatered or underwatered which may lead to their death. Over-watering can result in root rot which in the end kills the plant, yet under-watering can cause the plant to become dry and shriveled up and die (Ketsa & Warrington, 2023). Proper watering is vital to the growth and survival of indoor plants but failing to do so can greatly shorten their lives. In view of this, maintenance of indoor plants entails supply of the right amount of water needed for the plant's growth and survival.

The plant loses its stiffness in cells and tissues when insufficient water is received by the plant. An important problem concerning indoor plants that can lead to discoloration of leaves, curling of leaves, and droopiness is insufficient watering (Avigal et al, 2020). Self-irrigating pots can be helpful in this respect since they allow the plants that are grown in them to hydrate themselves and therefore make it possible to relax weekly watering schedules (Loewe, 2020). Therefore, sufficient water should be given at an appropriate time.

The study aims to design an Automatic Watering System for plants based on soil moisture sensors and an Arduino interface. The goal is to build a system that can monitor the soil moisture levels and irrigate plants, when necessary, thereby eliminating the need for human intervention. The correct level of soil moisture depends on factors like soil type and plant species. There is real time monitoring and control of the watering system with the use of soil moisture sensors

and Arduino interface. The proficiency of the machine in delivering the amount of water for the several types of house plants will be evaluated. Also, the threshold levels of moisture are identified that make the automatic watering system function. The results of this study could be applied in the industries of farming and automated plant maintenance.

Arduino is a simple board which can be used for programming or communication. Arduino is an accessible and reliable instrument for scholarly writing and research assignments, where the hardware and software are user-friendly (Louis, 2018). It can directly connect to multiple devices (e.g., relays, motors, and sensors), and has enough power to control the basic operations of the product (Pan, 2017). It is also a stand-alone program hence the board manages its running time and takes care of the several sensors and output devices connected to it that's why it is the best choice in the construction of interactive devices. The Arduino enables not only beginners but also the experts to not only build but also economically make things that actuate and sense the environment. Arduino interface is well-suited for a wide variety of applications related to environmental monitoring (Real et al., 2021).

Soil moisture sensors are a vital part of the equipment which is used to determine the moisture content of soil. The majority of sensors are probes, electronic circuits, and wiring cables. The calibration tests the sensor performed with a working range voltage from 2.5 volts to 5.5 volts. Such sensors are mobile - for instance, hand-held probes, or stationary. Through combining soil moisture sensors with auto-watering systems placed on the Arduino platform, the plant owners get the benefits of efficient water management, water conservation, better plant yields, and cost efficiency (Taneja, 2017).

Automatic Watering Systems provide- a precise and effective means of delivering water to plant roots while curbing water waste- from evaporation or imprecise watering. These systems are- engineered to gauge soil moisture at set intervals. When the moisture dips below a pre-established threshold tailored to a plant's watering needs, the system distributes the- required amount of water until the- threshold is met again (Punitha et al., 2018). By sensing soil moisture levels, the- device can supply exactly the- suitable water quantity for plants. Additionally, the system tracks the water tank level for optimal water management (Nandhini, 2018).

The current gadget in the market that has similar functionality as this research is the Automated Irrigation System from AG Middle East, but it differs from the product of this research as it does not feature a soil moisture sensor. In the case of market devices, a timer for watering the plant is also a feature of these web systems. As opposed to what was researched and discussed in which detects the low moisture level. This smart device also focuses on its functionality as an indoor watering device for houseplants, featuring a portable device with a battery-operated system and a built-in water tank for convenience.

By utilizing this device, it could lead to more eco-friendly and efficient watering practices as it only waters plants, when necessary, thus lowering water waste and minimizing environmental impact. Furthermore, plant health may improve by ensuring they receive appropriate amounts of water at optimal times which can decrease risks associated with over or under-watering that potentially damages the houseplant. Employing innovative technology such as soil moisture sensors in conjunction with the Arduino interface in the study creates a unique approach towards enhancing plant care techniques; This development might interest researchers researching similar implementation methods into their own areas of study focusing on sustainability solutions within various industries. Due to readily available components used in constructing the proposed irrigation mechanism like soil moisture sensors alongside the commonly utilized Arduino interfaces, cost effectiveness is observed via user friendly features observed while engaging with said device solution. This implies accessibility reaching varied demography including individuals lacking proficiency about technological aspects plus limited financial resources. The proposed device could be further refined, and the study could be expanded to investigate the device's impact on water usage, plant growth, and other factors.

II. RESEARCH QUESTIONS

The main objective of this study is to create an Automatic Watering Device for houseplants using soil moisture sensors and Arduino interface. Specifically, this study aims to address the following questions:

1. How accurate is the Automatic Watering Device moisture reading compared to a moisture meter?
2. How much water is required for the soil moisture sensor to detect moisture in the soil?
3. What is the optimal length of time that it takes for the soil moisture sensor to detect moisture?

III. HYPOTHESIS

It is feasible to make an automatic watering device for houseplants using soil moisture sensors and Arduino interface.

IV. METHODOLOGY

This study utilized the experimental design of research. Experimental research design is centrally concerned with constructing research that is high in causal (or internal) validity (Mitchell, 2015). The independent variables in this study are Soil Moisture Sensor and Arduino Interface while the dependent variable is an Automatic Water Device for house plants. The experiment is organized properly using a quantitative research methodology so that the right kind of data to answer the problem will be available. The procedure of gathering and performing a numerical analysis is called a quantitative method. It requires collecting data, analyzing, and interpreting quantifiable data to prove the hypothesis produced in a specific study. Quantitative method is used to summarize, average, find patterns, make predictions, and test causal associations as well as generalizing results to wider populations (Rana et al., 2021). This approach is necessary because it offers a high level of control over variables that shows some outcome and has an upper hand in getting accuracy, consistency as well as precision in its outcomes.

Research Locale

The research study was conducted in Philippine School Doha in Doha, State of Qatar, notably in the Mesaimmer Area (Zone 56), Al Khulaifat Al Jadeeda Street (St. 1011).

Data Gathering Procedure

The procedure shows the step-by-step process and instructs how to make an Automatic Water Device for house plants out of a soil moisture sensor and Arduino interface. Some of the steps listed in the process down below are referenced from a website called instructables.com (2016)

Ensuring protection and maintaining safety

1. Wear personal protective equipment while performing the procedures below to avoid hazardous conditions.

Gather the materials

1. Soil Moisture Sensor
2. Arduino Board
3. Breadboard
4. Wires and connections
5. Water Tube
6. Water Pump
7. Acrylic Plastic
8. Relay Module
9. Power Source (9-12V)
10. Super Glue
11. Hinge
12. PVC Pipe
13. PVC Elbow
14. PVC Coupling

Connecting the Arduino and soil moisture sensor:

1. Connect the VCC and GND pins of the soil moisture sensor to the 3.3V and GND pins on the Arduino board, respectively.
2. Connect the DO pin of the soil moisture sensor to a digital input pin on the Arduino board, specifically the ~6 pin.
3. Recheck the connections to make sure they are secure and correct.

Connect the Relay Module to the Arduino:

1. Connect the VCC and GND pins of the relay module to the 5V and GND pins on the Arduino board, respectively.
2. Connect the Out pin of the relay module to a digital input pin on the Arduino board, specifically the ~3 pin.
3. Recheck the connections to make sure they are secure and correct.

Connect the Relay Module to the Water Pump and the Power Source:

1. Identify the positive (red) and negative (black) wires of the power source.
2. Connect the negative (black) wire of the power source to the positive (red) wire of the water pump.
3. Secure the connection by wrapping the wire with electrical tape or heat-shrink tubing.
4. Carefully unscrew and insert the positive (red) wire of the power source to the COM (Common Contact) pin on the relay module.
5. Unscrew and insert the negative (black) wire of the water pump to the NO (Normally Open) pin on the relay module.
6. Recheck the connections

Writing the code

1. Write code to read the soil moisture value from the sensor and store it in a variable.
2. Write code to compare the soil moisture value to a threshold value (e.g. 400).
3. Write code to turn on the water pump when the soil moisture value is below the threshold and turn it off when it is above the threshold.
4. Open the Arduino Software.
5. Input the program, verify it, and upload it to the Arduino Interface microcontroller using the USB cable.

Code lines for Table 1

```

sketch_feb11a | Arduino IDE 2.2.2-nightly-20240116
File Edit Sketch Tools Help
Select Board

sketch_feb11a.ino
1 int moisturePin = A0; // Pin for soil moisture sensor (analog pin)
2 int relayPin = 3; // Pin for relay module
3
4 void setup() {
5   pinMode(relayPin, OUTPUT); // output pin for relay board
6   pinMode(moisturePin, INPUT); // Input pin coming from the soil sensor
7   Serial.begin(9600); // Initialize serial communication
8 }
9
10 void loop() {
11   int moisture = analogRead(moisturePin); // Reading the analog signal from the soil sensor
12
13   // Map the moisture reading to a percentage scale (adjust min and max values as needed)
14   int moisturePercentage = map(moisture, 0, 1023, 0, 100);
15
16   // Display moisture level in percentage on Serial Monitor
17   Serial.print("Moisture Level: ");
18   Serial.print(moisturePercentage);
19   Serial.println("%");
20
21   if (moisturePercentage < 30) // If soil moisture is below 30%, cut the relay to stop water supply
22   {
23     digitalWrite(relayPin, HIGH); // HIGH to cut the relay (assuming HIGH turns off the water pump)
24   }
25   else
26   {
27     digitalWrite(relayPin, LOW); // LOW to continue providing the signal and water supply
28   }
29
30   delay(400); // Adjust this delay as needed
31 }
Ln 31, Col 2 No board selected

```

Code lines for table 2 and 3

```

sketch_feb11a | Arduino IDE 2.2.2-nightly-20240116
File Edit Sketch Tools Help
Select Board

sketch_feb11a.ino
1 int moisture; // Variable to store soil moisture level
2 unsigned long activationStartTime = 0; // Variable to store the activation start time
3
4 void setup() {
5   pinMode(3, OUTPUT); // output pin for relay board, this will send a signal to the relay
6   pinMode(6, INPUT); // Input pin coming from the soil sensor
7   Serial.begin(9600); // Initialize serial communication
8 }
9
10 void loop() {
11   moisture = digitalRead(6); // Reading the incoming signal from the soil sensor
12
13   if (moisture == LOW) // If soil is dry (LOW moisture reading), cut the relay to stop water supply
14   {
15     digitalWrite(3, LOW); // LOW to cut the relay
16     if (activationStartTime == 0) {
17       // Record the activation start time only if it's the first time
18       activationStartTime = millis();
19     }
20   }
21   else
22   {
23     digitalWrite(3, HIGH); // HIGH to continue providing the signal and water supply
24     activationStartTime = 0; // Reset activation start time when the soil is not dry
25   }
26
27   // Print activation time to Serial Monitor
28   if (activationStartTime != 0) {
29     unsigned long activationTime = millis() - activationStartTime;
30     Serial.print("Activation Time: ");
31     Serial.print(activationTime);
32     Serial.println(" ms");
33   }
34
35   delay(400); // Adjust this delay as needed
36 }
Ln 36, Col 2 No board selected

```

Testing and Troubleshooting

1. Connect the power source to the Arduino board and turn on the device.
2. Calibrate the potentiometers by adjusting their values until you get the desired amount of water released for each plant.
3. Adjust the threshold value for the soil moisture sensor as necessary based on the plants' specific requirements.

4. Test the system to ensure that it is functioning as expected using Breadboard.
5. Recheck the connections and code to make sure that everything is in order.
6. Troubleshoot any issues that may arise and make necessary adjustments.

Assembling the Automatic Watering Device

1. Cut the acrylic plastic into its appropriate dimensions.
2. Stick them together with a superglue to form a rectangular base.
3. Drill holes on the base for the needed components.
4. Put the Arduino relay, the Arduino uno, soil moisture sensor, battery, and the breadboard in the acrylic plastic base and put them together by using a spacer and a nut.
5. Place the water pump on the designated water area of the base.
6. Put the water tube inside the water are of the base and
7. Put the PVC coupling, the PVC pipe, and the PVC elbow to create the faucet.
8. Add hinges to the lid of the acrylic plastic base for the device to be accessible and for water refill.
9. Test the system regularly and make adjustments as necessary.

Note: Safety precautions should be taken when drilling holes into the acrylic plastic base and when connecting electrical components. Use eye protection and wear gloves if necessary. Avoid touching the components or connections with wet hands, and always double-check the connections before turning on the power source.

V. RESULTS

This study aimed at creating an Automatic Watering Device using Soil Moisture Sensors and Arduino Interface. The section below presents the results and interpretations of the data collected during the testing procedure in order to answer three main research questions, namely its accuracy compared to a moisture meter, the volume of water dispensed, and the average time of activation.

1. Accuracy of the Automatic Watering Device moisture reading compared to a moisture meter

Table 1 Automatic Watering Device Accuracy Compared to a Soil Moisture Meter

Trial no.	1	2	3
Automatic Watering Device	3.9	4.8	6
Photos			
Moisture Meter	4	5	6
Accuracy	98.75%	98%	100%

Table 1 shows the three trials, where the accuracy of the Automatic Watering Device was compared to a moisture meter. Three pots of soil with different soil moisture levels were used for the three trials. A standard soil moisture meter, which is on a scale of one to 10, was used to compare the moisture level readings with the Automatic Watering Device. In comparison with a standard soil moisture meter, the Automatic Watering Device yielded 3.9 moisture while the moisture meter yielded a moisture level of 4 in the first trial. In the second trial, the Automatic Watering Device yielded out a moisture of 4.8 and in comparison, the soil moisture meter yielded out a moisture level of 5. In the third trial, both the moisture reading of the Automatic Watering Device and the moisture meter yielded the moisture level of 6. In a study conducted by Soulis et al. (2015), stated that a sensor's accuracy could be also an important factor affecting irrigation efficiency. The results of their study provided clear evidence that soil moisture sensor positioning and accuracy can considerably affect irrigation efficiency in soil moisture-based drip irrigation scheduling systems.

2. Water required for the Automatic Watering Device to detect moisture in the soil

Table 2 Water Requirement for Automatic Watering Device Detection

Trial No,	1	2	3
Photos			
Volume of water (ml)	120 ml	150 ml	190 ml
Flow of Water	Ongoing	Ongoing	Stopped

Table 2 shows the volume of water that is required for the Automatic Watering Device to detect moisture in the soil therefore activating the device. In these trials, the device was programmed to water a Carnation plant which requires 0.8 cups of water (189 ml). Border Carnation needs 0.8 cups of water every 9 days when it does not get direct sunlight and is potted in a 5.0" pot (Greg, 2022). In the first trial, the device was not triggered with a 120-milliliter volume of water. In the second trial, 150 milliliters of water triggered the device to activate. 190 milliliters of water triggered the device to activate in the third trial. In a study conducted by Kumar et al. (2019), water is one of the most important inputs in crop production. It influences almost all the physiological processes of the plant, that is why it is important to water only the necessary amount intended for that specific plant, in this case the marigold plant.

3. Optimal length of time for the Automatic Watering Device to detect moisture

Table 3 Optimal Time Length for Automatic Watering Device Detection

Trials	1	2	3	Average
Photos		$\frac{(5.45 + 7.64 + 9.40)}{3}$ $= 7.496666667$		
Time (seconds)	5.45 seconds	7.64 seconds	9.40 seconds	7.50 seconds

Table 3 presents the optimal length of time required for the Automatic Watering Device to detect moisture in the soil. In these trials, the time in the table indicates the overall time where the device was activated, which includes the relay module's response time, water pumping time, and soil moisture sensor detection time. In the first trial, the device was able to detect moisture in 5.45 seconds. In the second trial, it took 7.64 seconds for the device to detect moisture. In the third trial, the optimal length of time for the Automatic Watering Device to detect moisture was 9.40 seconds. All the trials resulted in an average time of 7.50 seconds for the Automatic Watering Device to detect moisture. The study of Yu et al. (2021) stated that soil moisture is directly related to the amount of irrigation in agriculture and influences the yield of crops. As a result, one crucial instrument for determining the moisture content of soil is a soil moisture sensor. Through calibration tests and field tests, it is necessary to accurately measure the soil profile moisture content in real-time and understand spatial water use, in order to provide a basis for selecting the optimal irrigation time and threshold and carrying out precision irrigation.

Hypothesis

This study's alternative hypothesis, which states that it is feasible to make an automatic watering device for houseplants using soil moisture sensors and Arduino interface, is accepted. A working watering device for houseplants that operates automatically, activates through the use of a Soil Moisture Sensor, dispenses the correct amount of water accurately, and is controlled using an Arduino Interface, was made.

VI. DISCUSSION

The risk of overwatering and underwatering plants has been an issue since the pandemic ended, resulting in plant owners returning to their regular routines, often leading them away from home to fulfill their duties. Under moisture stress conditions, the vegetative growth, yield, and quality of the fruits are significantly affected, however, the soil and crop environment are also affected by excess water through the depletion of oxygen, which leads to reduced root respiration and other vital plant processes (Kumar, 2019).

An Automatic Watering Device for houseplants was created that focuses on its adaptability, portability, and effectiveness with the use of soil moisture sensors as its indicator and an Arduino interface as its main board. This research strived for a favorable outcome relying on the accuracy of the device compared to a standard moisture meter. The volume of water it dispensed was analyzed before the Automatic Watering Device detected the moisture. Finally, the duration of time the device takes before it activates and deactivates was evaluated.

Based on the results of the study, in comparison with a standard soil moisture meter, the Automatic Watering Device can detect moisture with a promising average accuracy rate of 98%, establishing its reliability as a tool in detecting accurate levels of moisture in soil. Furthermore, the Automatic Watering Device demonstrates an efficient optimal length of time of soil moisture detection, with a computed average of 7.50 seconds. The Automatic Watering Device accurately dispensed the volume of water that was set in the device before it was triggered, where in this case was a Carnation plant that requires 190 ml of water. In conclusion, it is feasible to make an automatic watering device for houseplants using soil moisture sensors and Arduino interface, which supports the hypothesis.

The Automatic Watering Device developed for optimal houseplant care is seen as effective across all the important parameters. The research highlights the transformative nature of the Automatic Watering Device on houseplant care. With its consistent and precise water dispensing, coupled with a sensitive soil moisture sensor, its reliability as a tool for optimal plant growth has now been established. To conclude, the presented research puts forth a novel strategy addressing the issues caused by varying watering habits of indoor plants due to post-COVID-19 pandemic. The uniqueness of Arduino manifests in the aspect of real-time monitoring, highlighting the use of Arduino in automated plant care. Besides houseplant care, the study's impact may be applied to agriculture and automated plant maintenance industries as well. Future research should consider the device's adaptability and impacts on water and plant growth in order to determine its potential applications. By installing an Automatic Plant Watering Device, every houseplant can reach its full potential while saving water. We concluded that the Automatic Plant Watering Device becomes a big step towards automation in plant care, due to its efficiency, sustainability, and improved plant well-being. Moving forward, the study recommends a directive to refine soil moisture sensor thresholds for more accuracy in the Automatic Watering Device. The user-friendly interfaces development, smart home system integration exploration and extensive field testing with user feedback are proposed to improve accessibility and adaptability. Energy optimization and problems such as soil variability and different plant species are areas of future attention. Future studies should investigate the integration of Automatic Watering Devices with home automation systems, with the expectation of changing plant care in the households. With this integration, the device becomes more efficient within the framework and a new literature research stream on adaptability and scalability in automated plant care systems is born.

Future studies should also try to develop an app that can perform tasks such as set watering intervals, control the amount of water delivered, select for specific plant types through the app, and turn the whole device on and off to better utilize the device's automation and reduce the hands-on involvement of the plant owner. In the study of Astutiningtyas et al. (2021), in which they made a network called "Smart Garden" which is an electronic control and garden monitoring system for the process of watering plants. They utilized sensors as devices used for smart agriculture and used Arduino Uno which controls all system operations such as monitoring the plants watering system. Yu et al. (2021) states that this work extends the scope and suggests new avenues for research on dynamic changes in soil moisture and energy conversion, building on the findings of earlier studies which will greatly benefit the advancement of using soil moisture sensors in larger Automatic Systems and to bigger heights. Examining these integrations from a broader perspective, in view of the challenges and opportunities it presents, could prepare the ground for novel advancements within smart home gardening technologies thus potentially solving the problem of irregular watering patterns that may damage the houseplants.

VII. ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

The researchers wish to express their gratitude and appreciation to all those who supported and guided them throughout the study, especially to the following:

Dr. Alexander S. Acosta, the principal of the Philippine School Doha for letting the researchers experience crafting a research paper.

Dr. Lorina S. Villanueva, the QAAD Vice Principal and **Dr. Noemi F. Formaran**, the Senior High School Vice Principal, for allowing the researchers to conduct their study in the Grade 12 level.

Dr. Dave B. Buragay, the researchers' research advisor, for advising the researchers throughout the study.

Dr. Julie Ann B. Real, the researchers' Research teacher, for guiding and teaching the researchers throughout the study.

Mr. and Mrs. Escalona, Mr. and Mrs. Escobar, Mr. and Mrs. Anig, Mr. and Mrs. Laja, Mr. and Mrs. Diaz, and Mr. and Mrs. Salenga for supporting and motivating the researchers to finish the paper.

And mainly, our **Almighty God** for giving the researchers the strength and motivation all throughout the study.

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BIOGRAPHICAL SKETCH

Flynt Kieran A. Diaz is currently studying at the Philippine School Doha as a Grade 12-Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics (STEM) Senior High School student in Qatar. He is from Ozamis, Misamis Occidental, although born in Qatar. He spent all his previous years of education in Philippine School Doha, he has received top 10 awards throughout his academic years. He has joined extracurricular clubs throughout elementary to junior high school years including, boy scouts and badminton club. He won awards in intramural sports such as volleyball, badminton, table tennis and won 1st place in science fair competitions. He was able to complete his Junior High School years and marched during the

Convocation Ceremony. He believes that Success is not an accident, it is hard work, sacrifice, perseverance and most of all, love of what you do.

Lance Emmanuel M. Escalona is a Grade 12 Senior Highschool Student from Philippine School Doha. He is from Bauan, Batangas. He was born on March 12, 2006. Some of his achievements include being a Bronze Medalist in S.Y. 2018-2019 and S.Y. 2019-2020. He became a Silver Medalist in S.Y. 2020-2021. He participated in the Amazing Race in Grade 7; He got the highest score in Mathematics in the GRACE test in Grade 7 and he won the T-shirt Design Making Contest for Science Fair in Grade 8. He had been part of the top ten in his class quarterly for four consecutive years. Currently, he is taking up Science, Technology, Engineering, Mathematics (STEM) strand in Senior High School S.Y. 2023 - 2023. He was part of the Laureola during the first semester and was able to become a Silver Awardee. He likes to

think that everything you imagined getting will be yours as long as you have patience and dedication to what you want to achieve.

Prince Rovi C. Salenga is a Grade 12 Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics (STEM) Senior High School Student at Philippine School Doha. He is From Sta. Rita, Pampanga. He was born on January 08, 2006. Some of his achievements include being a consistent academic achiever in his Preschool, Primary, Intermediate, and Junior High School years. He transferred to Philippine School Doha during his 6th grade. He has been a consistent bronze awardee in Philippine School Doha. He was part of the Academic Olympiad contest in his school called Clash of the Wizards during his 8th grade and placed 1st. During his 1st senior high school year, he was part of the Laureola awardees during the 1st and 2nd semester and was able to receive the bronze award and silver award respectively. Then, during his 2nd senior high

school year, he was able to receive the silver award during the first semester. He believes that failure is a part of success and should not be feared. Failure is merely a stepping stone for us to be able to succeed in whatever goals we may have.

Louie Ashley B. Aniang is a Grade 12 Student from Philippine School Doha. She was born on November 3, 2006. She is from Novaliches, Quezon City, but she spent half of her life in Riyadh, Saudi Arabia where she was a successful student. She later moved to Qatar and started attending Philippine School Doha in the 6th grade. She is currently a STEM (Science, Technology, Engineering and Mathematics) student and the treasurer of the school's Academic Guild. She is also the treasurer of her section, a member of the project Eco, a member of the school's Qatar Senior Guides, a consistent member of the top 10 since grade 6, a Laureola awardee who placed top 3 in her batch, and a silver medal awardee from 2019-2023. She is very active with the activities in school, participating in numerous competitions, both inter school

and national, such as partaking in the PIMSO National Math Level Math Test in S.Y 2021-2022, where she was awarded with a bronze medal, PICE Qatar Math Whiz Contest finalist in 2022-2023, and the National Olympics for Creativity in Math, Science and Engineering in S.Y 2022-2023. With all the challenges she has been through, she learned that confidence is not only about one's outward appearance, but also about having faith in one's abilities and the courage to showcase them to the world.

Krisnelle Mae T. Escobar is a Grade 12 Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics (STEM) student in Philippine School Doha. She was born on June 25, 2006, in Doha, State of Qatar. She has been a consistent academic awardee. She has always been securing a spot for her in the Top 10 classroom academic achievers. She has received both bronze and silver medals in her past years in Junior and Senior High School. She has recently received a silver medal in S.Y. 2022-2024 and a bronze medal in S.Y. 2023-2024. Furthermore, she is a member of Dunong Academic Guild, an academic organization in school that requires above average performance in math and science to partake in it. She is the Medical and Safety officer of the said organization. She is also a member of Qatar Senior

Guides and Project Eco. She writes articles, writeups, and content in the school organizations she partakes in. Moreover, he has also recently played basketball in her team and finished as Champion. She also joined a chess tournament in S.Y. 2019-2020, S.Y. 2022-2023, and S.Y. 2023-2024. . She was also a finalist in the Academic Olympiad S.Y. 2015-2016. She participated in a poster making contest during the Science Fair S.Y. 2018-2019 and won 3rd place. She also placed

3rd along with her colleagues in the competition she joined for film making in S.Y. 2022-2023. She also joined several clubs like art, dance, glee, and guitar club during her intermediate and junior high school years. She aspires to become a neurosurgeon one day and believes that everything beautiful in this world starts with love.

Putli Tarhata R. Laja is a Grade 12 Senior Highschool Student from Philippine School Doha. She spent her elementary days in the Philippines while having received numerous academic recognitions. She is currently taking the Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics (STEM) academic track. She had received the Bronze Medalist back in Junior High in Grades 7, 9, and 10. Additionally, She was able to attain a bronze and silver medal during her time in the Senior High School Department from Grades 11 and 12; a consistent Laureolan. Outside of academics, She was also an active member of the Scouting Committee for seven years and spent five years as a Qatar Scout. Furthermore, She was also part of the Intermediate Math Club and is a Cartoonist for the campus journalism organization known as The Link. She hopes to take a course related to medicine in the near

future and believes that with effort and time, anything is possible.

